

Research Article

The Impact of Leadership Style on Employee's Performance-An Analysis on the Effect of Leadership Style on Staff Retention: Case Study, Rokel Commercial Bank, Sierra Leone

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Received: December 18, 2023

Accepted: January 07, 2024

Published: January 15, 2024

Abstract

Most scholars emphasize the transformational leadership style while acknowledging the importance of transactional leadership style. The study was guided by four objectives including: 1) To determine the effect of autocratic leadership style on employee's job performance. 2) To ascertain the effect of the leadership style adopted by the bank managers on employee performance. 3) To examine the impact of laissez faire leadership style on employee job performance. 4) To evaluate how RC Bank S/L's leadership style affects workers' performance. A total of 70 questionnaires were completed and useful for analysis out of 110 questionnaires that were issued. This represented a response rate of 70% and a non-response rate of 40%. The non-response rate was attributed to refusal to respond by respondents because of their busy schedules at work and other related issues within the working environment. Based on the findings obtained and the conclusion drawn in addressing the problems identified, the researcher forwarded the following recommendations as a possible solution to be considered by respected body. According to the ways the leaders enhances his or her employee's performance few of the respondents shows that leaders use punishment, in this situation even though the majority of the employee are treated and encouraged in a good manner for minority also, it is recommended not to react through punishment to any of the workers, rather than it is preferable to adopt other positive mechanism like training to motivate them and built their capacity to do the assigned jobs as per the requirements.

Keywords: Leadership Style, Employee's, Staff Retention, Rokel Commercial Bank, Sierra Leone.

Introduction

In corporations, religious institutions, educational institutions, and governmental institutions alike, leadership is essential to daily existence. The leadership of any business nowadays must be strong and determined in managing the affairs of the organization. According to research, there have been numerous discussions on leadership challenges in the modern world. A number of governments and organizations have failed as a result of poor leadership. Followership is a necessary component of leadership, and leadership can either deter or inspire followership. Particularly in an organization, the leadership style impacts how well the followers perform overall. In other words, a strong leadership style inside a company can significantly impact the productivity of its staff. According to Schyns and Sanders' (2007) research, one of the major governments and companies must look for effective leaders and leadership philosophies in order to become stronger and engage in the competitive global market and world politics of today. When there is a strong leadership style in place, organizational productivity is greatly increased. In their study of Nigerian banks, Ojokuku *et al.*, (2012) made the claim that effective leadership, particularly in the country's banking industry, is the primary factor of organizational performance.

Williams (2009) made the observation that the organization's outputs and performance are very much tied to the distinctive leadership style of the organization's leaders. One of the main forces behind economic growth and development on a global scale is the banking industry. According to Ebong's (2006) study on the banking industry's impact on economic growth, the banking sector serves as a mediator between various economic units with surplus funds and the government. Economic growth is facilitated by investment. By

pooling investor funds and assisting clients in borrowing money to expand their enterprises, banks can generate economies of scale that are advantageous for economic growth. One of the main forces behind Sierra Leone's economic development, sustainability, and progress has been the banking industry; over time, there have been mergers between various banks throughout the country's banking sector as well as bank failures of all sizes. The ineffective administration and leadership of those banks, as well as the recent acquisition of the former FIB bank by the Vista bank group of companies, were blamed for a large portion of the financial issues that Sierra Leone encountered (Okafor, 2010). Before being acquired, FIB Bank experienced a management crisis that was widely publicized as a poor example of bank leadership. The bank's then-CEO delegated responsibilities of the bank's affairs to a female assistant manager.

In agreement with (Bass, 1995) research, which found that transactional leadership style has a negative impact on organizational outputs. Johnson *et al.*, (2012) found that transactional leadership style is a positive predictor of employee performance after looking at the relationship between leader-member exchanges, transformational leadership, and transactional leadership in estimating employee performance. According to study (Bass *et al.*, 2012), transactional leadership enhances the effectiveness of the military. According to Elenkov's (2002) research on the relationship between leadership style and organizational performance, Russian managers who use a transactional leadership style have a beneficial impact on the productivity and loyalty of their workforce. According to Lievens *et al.*, (2007), transformational leadership styles are crucial for businesses to implement innovation more effectively, particularly in times of market competition or intra-organizational rivalry. According to Palanichamy and Raja (2011), a transformational leader's style boosts productivity without adding to the workload for the organization or the employees. This investigation's main goal was to determine how Rokel Commercial Bank's workers performed in respect to the practices of leadership style.

Review of Related Literature

Empirical Reviews

Numerous empirical studies have shown that leadership behaviors have an impact on employee performance, that strong leaders outperform weak leaders, and that transformational leadership results in higher performance than transactional leadership (Burns, 1978; Bass, 1990; Hater and Bass, 1985; Howell and Avolio, 1993). Thus, it is anticipated that both transactional and transformational leadership will directly improve employee performance. Raja and Palanichamy (2011) studied how different leadership philosophies affected worker performance in India's public and private businesses. The study's findings from 43 middle-level managers and 156 subordinates provide enough proof, at the 5% level of significance, that there is a linearly positive relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance as well as a significant positive relationship between transactional leadership and employee performance. However, the study discovered that lax leadership had a bad impact on employee outcomes and performance. One of the subjects that have received the most research in recent years is leaders and their leadership philosophies. The impact of different leadership philosophies on workforce productivity has been the subject of numerous studies.

Rassol *et al.*, (2015) investigated leadership styles and their effects on employees' performance in the Pakistani health sector and came to the conclusion that transformational leadership styles had a more favorable impact on employee performance than transactional leadership. They discovered that transformative leadership can function more effectively in an atmosphere that is extremely organic and focused on competitive advantages. The findings of their study also revealed that transactional leadership had a less significant effect on job performance than transformational leadership. Pradeep and Prabhu (2011) assert that both transactional contingent reward leadership behaviors and transformational leadership behaviors are positively correlated with employee performance. The managers, who are thought to exhibit strong leadership traits, whether transformational or transactional, are seen to be working to improve the productivity of their staff members.

In summarizing their findings, it was discovered that the transformational leadership style has a substantial association with performance outcomes, specifically work effectiveness, satisfaction, extra effort, and dependability. Their research contributed some new information to a better understanding of the preferred leadership style and strategy to use with subordinates at various professional levels. As a result of adopting the findings, leaders can modify their conduct in useful ways to improve the performance of their subordinates, which will boost productivity for their organizations as a whole. They place emphasis on the necessity for leaders to be able to entice and influence their subordinates, be able to set clear performance criteria for their peers, and serve as the best possible role model for the subordinates. In a study on nurses'

perceptions of managers' leadership styles and its associated outcomes, Aboshaiqah *et al.*, (2016) found that staff nurses believed transformational leadership and its factors were used more frequently than transactional and laissez-faire leadership styles. Further analysis also revealed a positive correlation between the outcome factors (effectiveness, satisfaction, and loyalty) and also employees are motivated to do more work more and happy with the transformational and transactional leadership styles been experience at the work place, than the laissez-faire leadership style been showcase in the in the past. They came to the conclusion that a variety of transformational leadership behaviors, styles, and characteristics increased nurses' perceived leader effectiveness, additional effort, and total employee performance. In a study by Ispas and Babaita (2012) on perceived leadership style and worker performance in the hotel business, it was discovered that managers who consistently achieve the desired results are thought to adopt autocratic leadership style. Furthermore, they emphasized the need for managers to come up with effective strategies for assisting staff members in enhancing their own performance.

A study on the effect of leadership philosophies on worker performance was also conducted by Obasan Kehinde and Hassan Banjo (2014). According to a study conducted by the Department of Petroleum Resources, "transformational leadership style" would produce effective results in organizations because it inspires workers to go above and beyond what is expected of them, speaks to followers' higher-order needs and moral values, ignites their passion for the organization's mission and values, instills their sense of pride and confidence, communicates their respect for one another, and stimulates their sense of self-worth. The results of its associated studies showed that staff nurses believed that transformative leadership and (efficiency, extra work, and contentment) and transactional and transformational leadership styles, as well as a bad link with laissez-faire leadership style. They came to the conclusion that a variety of transformational leadership behaviors, styles, and characteristics increased nurses' perceived leader effectiveness, additional effort, and total employee performance. In a study by Ispas and Babaita (2012) on perceived leadership style and worker performance in the hotel business, it was discovered that managers who consistently achieve the desired results are thought to adopt autocratic leadership style. Furthermore, they emphasized the need for managers to come up with effective strategies for assisting staff members in enhancing their own performance.

Methodology

The research approach is explained in chapter three, which also takes into account the study area, Rokel Commercial Bank Head Quarter S/L. Additionally; it will describe the source of the data, the research design, the research analysis, the questionnaire design, and other parts of the research analysis. In order to achieve the goal of this study, the normative survey approach was employed to look at the relationship between leadership style and staff performance at RCB headquarters. The whole management and staff of the RCB Freetown headquarters make up the study population. Among the bank managers and bank staff, a random sample size was chosen. The selection of 50 bank employees and ten bank managers was done at random. 50 RC bank employees and 10 RC bank managers make up the final research sample for this study.

The researcher in this study employed both primary and secondary data gathering techniques to gather the required data. An open-ended and a closed-ended questionnaires used, which was produced and given to the respondents for more in-depth information, the questionnaires was utilized as the major data collection tools to gather information from respondent. The questionnaire was utilized by the researcher since it is crucial to maximize the likelihood that the employees will provide truthful information. Direct quotes from written sources such books, articles, and the internet were used to gather secondary data. The replies that were unclear were cut off. Given that this study was an original study, the sources of the data were both primary and secondary. As was previously stated, the primary instrument utilized to gather data was a closed-and open-ended questionnaire for respondents. With the aforementioned staff categories, in-person interviews were undertaken. The researcher and the respondents worked out when the administration should take place. The researcher helped facilitate the dissemination of the questionnaires and helped with data collection. Because some responders were too busy with office job, the entire exercise took place over the course of two months.

Results

ATA Analysis and Presentations

The table below indicated that 78.6% of the respondents agree that the bank has a good employee relation that exist between the employees and employers at all level of management, and 21.4% disagree that the bank has little or no form of employee relationship in the place of work. Meaning majority of the employee

working at the bank agree that the bank has some significant increase in-terms of employee relations at all level of management.

Table 1. Is there any unique leadership style been practice at RC bank Sierra Leone?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent
Yes	55	78.6	78.6
No	15	21.4	21.4
Total	70	100.0	100.0
Source: Field survey 2023			

Table 2. What type of relationship been practice at RC bank Sierra Leone?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent
Cordial relationship	45	64.28	64.28
Strong relationship	10	14.32	14.32
Weak relationship	15	21.4	21.4
Total	70	100.0	100.0
Source: Field survey 2023			

The table above shows that 64.28% of the respondents indicated that the bank practice a cordial relationship among employees and employers within the bank, 14.32% said that there is a strong relationship among staff and 21.4% indicated that the bank practice the weakest form of employee relations than its competitors in the banking sector. Meaning 64.28% of the respondents indicated that the bank practice a cordial relationship among employees and employers within the bank.

Table 3. Is there any impact made by the leadership style adopted at RC bank?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent
Yes	45	64.28	64.28
No	25	35.72	35.72
Total	70	100.0	100.0
Source: Field survey 2023			

The table above reveals that 64.28% of the respondents indicated there is a high impact made by employees at Rokel Commercial Bank, 35.72%, indicated that the employees contribute less towards organizational performance at Rokel Commercial Bank. Meaning 64.28% of the respondents indicated there is a high impact made by employees at Rokel Commercial Bank.

Table 4. Type of employee's impact at RC bank.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent
Increase in market-share	15	21.4	21.4
Customer satisfaction	40	57.2	57.2
Quality service	15	21.4	21.4
Total	70	100.0	100.0
Source: Field survey 2023			

The table above reveals that 21.4% of the respondents indicated that there is an increase in market share, which has move customers interest than before, 57.2% indicated that there is a significant increase in customer satisfaction which is one of the most important factor that leads to organization and competitive edge over rivals in the banking industry, and 21.4% indicated that there is a high amount of quality in service delivery at Rokel Commercial Bank which holds most of their customer together.

Table 5. How does RC bank go about maintaining employee's relationship and job satisfaction?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent
Reward	10	14.3	14.3
Appraisal	40	57.2	57.2
Compensation	20	28.5	28.5
Total	70	100.0	100.0
Source: Field survey 2023			

The table above reveals that 14.3% of the respondents indicated that the Bank maintain employees job satisfaction through by rewarding them for good work. 57.2% of the respondents totally agree that employees job satisfaction can only be achieved if and only if embark on appraisals annually, and 28.5% indicated that compensation goes a long way with employee job satisfaction.

Table 6. Does the change of top management create any impacts on the performance of RC bank?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent
Yes	40	57.2	57.2
No	30	42.8	42.8
Total	70	100.0	100.0

Source: Field survey 2023

The table above reveals that 57.2% of the respondents indicated there is a high impact made by employees through participation and involvement in different management activities across all levels at Rokel Commercial Bank. 42.8% indicated that the change of management has less to do with employee’s voice through participation or contribution at Rokel Commercial Bank.

Table 7. What are the impacts on organizational performance?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent
High	40	57.2	57.2
Moderate	20	28.5	28.5
Low	10	14.3	14.3
Total	70	100.0	100.0

Source: Field survey 2023

The table above reveals that 57.2% of the respondents indicated the bank has increase it performance after undertaking a structural reform process by encouraging employee participation as a tool for better performance and organizational growth. 28.5% indicated that, even though the bank has undertaken reformation process by encouraging employee’s contribution yet still the performance as it used to be before. 14.3% still have the convection that the bank performance is nothing to write home about (low) even though employees’ participation has been incorporated in to decision making process at management level.

Table 8. What are challenges facing managers in implementing their leadership style at RC bank?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent
Slow decision making	20	28.5	28.5
Lack of experience	40	57.2	57.2
Waste of time	10	14.3	14.3
Total	70	100.0	100.0

Source: Field survey 2023

The table above reveals that 28.5% of the respondents indicated that one of the challenges face by the bank in enhancing employees participation is slow decision making, 57.2% indicated that due to lack of experience by most of the employees working at Rokel bank has brought so many challenges by incorporating employees voice into the organization, and 14.3% indicated that because management want to discourage delayed in decision making and rid out in-experience staff; they see employee voice as a challenge through by wasting time.

Table 9. What are the effects of leadership style on staff retention at RC bank?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent
Innovation	40	57.2	57.2
Increase in productivity	15	21.4	21.4
Reduce staff turnover	15	21.4	21.4
Total	70	100.0	100.0

Source: Field survey 2023

The table above shows that 57.2% of the respondents indicated that one of the greatest factors affecting employees voice at Rokel bank is lack of good policy development and implementation, 21.4% indicated that management is not interested in employees voice contribution, and 21.4% indicated that because

management realize that employee's participation has less or no contribution towards organizational performance so there is no need to incorporate it into the system.

Suggest Ways by Which RC Bank Should Implement Good Employee Relations Practices at the Work Place

By allowing employees to say their mind what they think about the organization:

- ✓ By involving them in all decision making at all management level.
- ✓ The means and factors of production most are control by the employees.
- ✓ Their contribution must be recognized at all time.
- ✓ Promotion, appraisals, rewards, training and development and job security can lead to job satisfaction.

Summary of Findings

From the responses of the respondents to the questionnaire the leaders answer for the questions are summarized as follows:

- ✓ From the total study of population, majority (78.6%) of the employees are females which imply the existence of female are greater than males in the bank. As we gain from the findings of the study, most of the workers (50%) in the organization were the age between 18-30 years.
- ✓ When we see the educational level of the employee, the majorities (42.0%) of the respondents were diploma; based on the job status of the workers, the majority (35.7%) of the respondents were supervisor.
- ✓ According to the department and functions of the respondents, at most (42.8%) of the employee work under the operations unit. According to the respondents response based on the years of existence of the organization, (64.3%) believed that the organization has been in existence for over 11-20 years. It was also agreed that, (42.8) of the function of the organization is accepting deposit from customer and (71.42) agree that the bank is large by size.

Summary and Conclusion

Following is a summary of the leaders' answers to the questions based on the questionnaire respondents' responses:

- ✓ According to the population research as a whole, the majority (55.84%) of the employees are men, indicating that there are more men than women in the firm.
- ✓ According to the study's findings, the majority of employees in the firm (37.5%) were between the ages of 36 and 40.
- ✓ The majority (77.58%) of the respondents were first-degree holders when looking at the employee's educational background.
- ✓ The majority (62.07%) of respondents were married according to the workers' marital status.
- ✓ The majority (39.66%) of employees were paid an income between \$3,500 and \$4,500 per month, according to the respondents' monthly income wage.
- ✓ According to the respondents' responses from many employees indicate that, the leader can influence an employee's performance through providing encouragement.
- ✓ As shown in various responses, the majority of respondents were informed that the leader controls the employee performance by penalizing them by cutting their compensation in order to manage their effort.
- ✓ According to the respondents' responses about salary reductions inside the organization, the majority of respondents (43.75%) think that salary reductions should be made.
- ✓ As shown in data collection, the majority of respondents (73.33%) indicated that the organization engages in bottom-up decision making, which fosters employee participation and places responsibility on employees.
- ✓ According to the research, the minority of the employees stated top-bottom decision making is exercised; as a result, the leader solves all of the problems and makes all of the decisions.
- ✓ The majority of respondents used the bottom-up decision-making method because it stimulates employee participation, as shown by the information gathered on this research work, and because it results in more decisions being taken.
- ✓ The majority of respondents stated that the participative leadership style is the one that the business uses in relation to the data in the report.
- ✓ According to the employees' responses regarding the methods used by the leaders to motivate them to perform their jobs effectively, these methods included raising the annual salary, reviewing staff

performance, providing staff training and assessment before providing the staff with training within the organization, supervision by scoring employees according to their performance, bottom-top decision making, participatory decision making, staff supervision, individual work plans, and technical support.

- ✓ This study attempted to evaluate how a leader's actions in an organization affect the productivity of their team members and their job functions. It also sought to identify the leadership philosophies that the organization uses. The study's goal was to better understand the effects of leadership style on employee performance.
- ✓ Notably, the study outlined how the growing use of encouragement enables leaders to boost staff performance and hence facilitate participation in internal consultancy. This admission suggests that leaders will largely rely on staff incentive and encouragement to boost their performance.
- ✓ The majority of employees in the organization responded that the leader used participatory leadership, which suggests that it has a greater positive impact on employee performance in situations where employees feel empowered and confident in doing their jobs and in making different decisions. The leader gave his/her subordinates the opportunity to participate in decision-making and increased their confidence in meeting for difficult tasks.
- ✓ In accordance with the majority of respondents' responses, they benefited from offering advice. This suggests that the leader was also acting as a mentor to his or her followers in addition to supervising workers.
- ✓ The general consensus from the study is that the manager or leader has a significant impact on how well employees perform, but the extent of that impact also depends heavily on the style of leadership in the firm. Despite the limited sample size, it is nevertheless advisable to use caution when generalizing the study's findings because they serve as the foundation for further investigation.

Recommendations

The researcher sent the following recommendations to a reputable body as a potential solution for consideration based on the findings attained and the conclusions reached in order to solve the issues highlighted:

- ✓ Although the majority of employees are treated and encouraged in a positive manner for minority as well, according to the ways that leaders improve their employees' performance, only a small percentage of respondents indicated that leaders use punishment. In this situation, it is advised not to react to any of the workers through punishment; instead, it is preferable to adopt other positive mechanisms like training to motivate them and build their capacity to do the assigned jobs.
- ✓ Based on feedback from respondents, some respondents indicated that decisions made during problem solving are typically made by a single leader. In this situation, the researcher advised that it is preferable to be participative and shared with the organization's employees.
- ✓ The organization's leader is advised to continue supervising the employees using participatory type of leadership since the majority of the workers were informed that this style of leadership has positive effects on worker performance and job satisfaction.

Declarations

Acknowledgments: We thank the Almighty Allah/God for giving us the opportunity and strength to write this research article. We want to thank the following people for their help towards this academic research work. We would like to express our sincere thanks and appreciation to our able supervisor's Dr. Ernest Udeh a member of the research team and Dr. Victor Moinina, without whom this work would have not been successful and to all our colleague lecturers at IPAM-USL that have help us in diverse ways through this research work. This work cannot yield any dividends if we fail to acknowledge our families especially our wives, husband's, children's and relatives and to our respondent at Rokel Commercial Bank Sierra Leone. All we could say that those whose names are not mentioned here, is that we appreciate them very much and may God continue to bless us all!

Author Contributions: SAK: Developed the concept, literature survey, statistical analysis, and manuscript review; EU: Developed the concept, design, literature survey, statistical analysis, manuscript review; BOD: Design, revision, literature survey, data collection, data analysis.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Consent to Publish: The authors agree to publish the paper in International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research.

Data Availability Statement: The data presented in this study are available upon request from the corresponding author.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Research Content: The research content of manuscript is original and has not been published elsewhere.

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Citation: Santigie Abu Kamara, Ernest Udeh and Blossom Onike Decker. 2024. The Impact of Leadership Style on Employee's Performance-An Analysis on the Effect of Leadership Style on Staff Retention: Case Study, Rokel Commercial Bank, Sierra Leone. *International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research*, 8(1): 1-9.

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